

RISK FACTORS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND RECURRENCE OF
NONSPECIFIC LARYNGEAL GRANULOMA

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Annotation: This article covers the important information about risk factors for the development and recurrence of nonspecific laryngeal granuloma. On the other hand, causes and treatment of developing of recurrence of nonspecific laryngeal granuloma were noted.

Key words: *conservative treatment, benign tumor, contact granuloma, laryngeal structures, inflammation, hammer and anvil, gastroesophageal reflux, Fatigued voice.*

Health and well-being are essential aspects of our lives that significantly impact our overall quality of life. Understanding and nurturing these different facets can lead to a more fulfilling and balanced life. Nonspecific granuloma of the larynx is a benign tumor that usually occurs on the posterior glottis. Recurrences frequently occur even when these granulomas are surgically resected and it is not rare for multiple repeated operations to be required. Therefore, conservative treatment using primarily a beclomethasone dipropionate inhaler (Aldecine(R) inhaler) was instituted in 20 cases of nonspecific granuloma of the larynx with good results. Nonspecific granuloma of the larynx is a benign tumor that usually occurs on the posterior glottis. Recurrences frequently occur even when these granulomas are surgically resected and it is not rare for multiple repeated operations to be required. Therefore, conservative treatment using primarily a beclomethasone dipropionate inhaler (Aldecine(R) inhaler) was instituted in 20 cases of nonspecific granuloma of the larynx with good results.

Vocal process granuloma (VPG) is first described by Chevalier Jackson in 1928 as “contact ulcer of the larynx”. It is also known by many names including; contact granuloma, vocal fold granuloma (VFG), post-intubation granuloma, and arytenoid granuloma. Vocal fold granulomas (VFGs) are benign lesions occurring from irritation of laryngeal structures on the vocal process of the arytenoid cartilage. As the mucosal covering in this area is a thin layer of stratified squamous epithelium, it is susceptible to being crushed by any object inserted into the glottis (e.g., tracheal or nasogastric tubes) and the cartilage beneath it, leading to inflammation and benign granuloma development. Jackson and Jackson, suggested that superficial ulceration and focal granulation result from a “hammer and anvil” action between both vocal processes[2]. The etiology of VFG is still undetermined and it is mainly attributed to various factors: gastroesophageal reflux (GER) or sometimes named laryngopharygeal reflux (LPR), endotracheal intubation, vocal abuse, habitual throat clearing, low-pitched voice, and psychosomatic disorders. Smoking, postnasal drip, and throat infections may also be causative agents. The designation of “idiopathic” VFG is given as a diagnosis of exclusion which posits that another etiology may exist. Patients suffering from a granuloma on the vocal cords generally experience:

- Severe hoarseness
- Change in voice pitch
- Discomfort or pain in the throat
- Fatigued voice

At Tampa General Hospital, our team of laryngologists take a patient-first approach in treating vocal cord granulomas. Effective treatment for the condition begins with accurate diagnosis. Depending on the cause of your laryngeal granuloma, our medical professionals may recommend using the following conservative, non-surgical treatment methods:

- Voice therapy
- Use of inhaled corticosteroids

- Use of proton pump inhibitors (PPI)
- Lifestyle changes that prevent reflux

In situations when the diagnosis of a laryngeal granuloma is made late, when the inflamed mass is so large that it may block the airway or when a once-treated granuloma has reappeared, surgery is often warranted.

Laryngeal granulomas (LG) belong to late, minor, postoperative complications following TLM. LG and glottic web constitute 22% of all complications and affect more likely patients after TLM involving the anterior commissure (AC)³. LG are mucosal lesions consisting of granulation tissue and arise as tissue's response to injury and irritation⁴. Lee et al. proved that the frequency of aforementioned complications following TLM depends on surgeon's experience and the size of the tumor². Most often, LG occurs within 1 or 2 months after surgery⁴. According to the literature, there is no dedicated treatment for LG. There are two approaches: (1) conservative therapy (antireflux therapy, voice therapy, botulin toxin, mitomycin C, steroids) and (2) surgery⁵. Proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) are widely used to treat LG, as laryngopharyngeal reflux is present in up to 76% of affected patients. Surgical methods, CO2 laser or cold instruments, are faster than conservative therapy, however, they involve a significant risk of local scarring and recurrence. Surgery is traditionally reserved for persisting cases⁵. Although LG are purely benign lesions, there is always a concern of the cancer recurrence within LG or in the surrounding tissue. NBI is a reliable blue light endoscopy, which is widely used in the detection of early head and neck cancers by assessing mucosal vascular pattern. Thereby, the aim of this study was to evaluate NBI in the differentiation between postoperative laryngeal granuloma and local tumor recurrence.

The inhaler contained a suspension of beclomethasone dipropionate, whose structural formula is shown in Figure. Sealed in an atomizer. The atomizer releases approximately 0.05 mg per spray. Two inhalations (a dose of approximately 0.1 mg) were given four times a day contained a suspension of beclomethasone

dipropionate, whose structural formula. The atomizer releases approximately 0.05 mg per spray. Two inhalations (a dose of approximately 0.1 mg) were given four times a day based on the protocol for the treatment of bronchial asthma. All of the patients were instructed to refrain from unnecessary coughing and loud talking. Therapeutic efficacy was assessed by local findings in the larynx observed with a laryngoendoscope. We established our own assessment criteria for therapeutic efficacy, classifying the results as excellent, good, fair, or poor.

One of the 20 patients who had an excellent response is presented here. Patient number 7 was a 50-year-old man whose chief complaint was coughing and hoarseness. He developed a mild cough in January 1990, and complained of hoarseness that made it difficult to produce a high-pitched voice in July 1990. He first presented to our clinic in August 1991. Flexible laryngofiberscopy revealed a grayish-white, spherical mass observed on the left vocal process of the arytenoid cartilage. Since the lesion appeared to be an idiopathic nonspecific granuloma of the larynx, beclomethasone dipropionate inhalation therapy was started. After approximately 1 week, his symptoms gradually improved, and after 4 weeks of inhalation therapy, the site of lesion had been reduced by approximately 50%.

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that nonspecific granuloma of the larynx most often arises on the posterior glottis, and laryngoendoscopic diagnosis is generally easy in many cases. However, these lesions must be differentiated from neoplasms such as laryngeal carcinoma and papilloma. Therefore, when no abnormal findings exist on general examination and clinical suspicion of nonspecific granuloma is high, the treatment plan described below is used in our clinic. Conservative therapy predominantly using a beclomethasone dipropionate inhaler is prescribed for 3 months for both idiopathic and post-intubation granuloma. In addition, unnecessary throat-clearing is discouraged, and patients are instructed to refrain from loud talking and to remain silent whenever possible. If the size of the lesion diminishes after 3 months, conservative therapy is continued for another 3 months and the patient's course is

followed. If, however, the lesion has not resolved after 6 months, or if no changes occur after the first three months, the lesion is resected surgically and examined histopathologically.

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